

اطفال کی تربیت سیرت طیبہ ﷺ کے آئینے میں ایک تحقیقی جائزہ

RESEARCH STUDY OF UPBRINGING OF CHILDREN IN THE MIRROR OF SEERAT-E-TAYYABA (ﷺ)**Muhammad Hamza (ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5715-5941)**

Assistant Professor, Department of Education, University Of Makran, Panjgur, Balochistan.

Rabia (ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4779-0578)

Ph.D. Research Scholar, Department of Islamic Learning, University of Karachi.

Uzma Mohammad Younus (ORCID ID: 0000-0003-3448-2258)

Ph.D. Research Scholar, Department of Islamic Learning, University of Karachi.

ABSTRACT

Modern World education pays more attention towards children where their perceptions, education, and reasoning got more prominent position. This 21st century's educational system wanted emotionally and psychologically better and strong child that can only be achieved through better upbringing. Scholars defined term Upbringing as, the treatment and instruction received by a child from its parents throughout its childhood.

In the whole process, educationists had adopted Children centric approach where their upbringing and socialization has more importance. But Islam as a religion got the child centric system much before where Prophet (ﷺ) trained child as a better citizen, problem solver, follower of moral values and also a better Muslim who can better serve society. Similarly, by taken various examples of upbringing of children by Prophet (ﷺ), one will be able to find out that, upbringing of children is also the duty of Parents as well as teachers as profession of teacher is also related to prophet hood. Therefore, teacher has a responsibility to play a role in inculcating high qualities in children. Similarly, the training of parents is very important for children's upbringing. The article gives a research review of children's upbringing in Islam by having precedents from life of Prophet (ﷺ). However, this research article also proposed that teachers and parents should play their constructive role in the development of positive behavior in children.

Keywords: Upbringing, Child Centric Educational Approach, Perception, Reasoning.

کلیدی الفاظ: اطفال، تربیت، پرورش، سیرت طیبہ، اسلامی تعلیمات۔

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7526222